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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“WHERE QUESTIONS BLOSSOM”

I walked a path where questions live,
where silence waits for those who give.
In pages worn, in voices near,
I searched for truths my heart held dear.

A teacher's hands, a scholar's pen,
I shaped the dreams of restless men.
Their doubts became my guiding flame,
their struggles carved my teaching name.

Like mothers feed a child in need,
I fed their minds with hope and seed.
Fear gave way to steady light,
and silence blossomed into flight.

But storms would rise, and shadows fall,
fatigue would press, despair would call.
Yet love and faith restored my song,
and urged my weary steps along.

Now here I stand, with lessons clear,
a voice to share, for all to hear.
Teacher and seeker, roles entwined—
a lifelong learner, heart aligned.

